

CONSUMING THE BODY IMAGE. YOUNG CHILDREN'S PERCEPTIONS OF BODY PORTRAYALS IN TELEVISION ADVERTISING

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1. EXPLORING CHILDREN'S ADVERTISING SKILLS

The body has become an object of interest in advertising. It may take a few seconds to realize that almost any brand utilizes the body to draw consumer attention as a part of its communication strategy. The use of the body in advertising is often legitimized by sociocultural narratives and references (Zayer *et al.*, 2019). The selection of archetypical features is not a random event but the personification of brands in an attempt to appeal to consumers' culture (Caldas-Coulhard, 2008). Paradoxically, the representations of the body in advertising also highlight contentious issues such as the exploitation of the body ideals to persuade its audience (Del Rosso, 2017; Hati, 2022).

Advertising captures the attention of most people, but children have a particularly strong bond with its message. Children as young as two can easily react to colors and music (Oates *et al.*, 2002), and as they grow, they develop the ability to remember brands, logos, and jingles (Aktaş-Arnas *et al.*, 2016; López & Rodríguez, 2018). However, the effectiveness of advertising messages may be moderated by individual barriers, such as levels of advertising literacy (Livingstone & Helsper, 2006; O'donohoe, 2001). Despite their ease of engagement and arousal, children have and continue to develop a variety of skills that allow them to comprehend and deal with advertising messages.

Advertising Literacy has emerged as a novel approach to exploring people's competence in understanding advertising. In the field of childhood and consumption studies, Advertising Literacy studies have contributed to a better understanding of how minors read, interpret, and cope with advertising (Rozendal *et al.*, 2011a; Vanwesenbeeck *et al.*, 2016).

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Although traditionally research has explored children's advertising literacy skills from a wider perspective such as children's reaction to food advertising and toy advertisements (Ha *et al.*, 2018; Hudders *et al.*, 2018; Spielvogel & Terlutter, 2013), little research has focused on children's abilities to understand body image in advertising. This study, therefore, aimed to analyze young children's advertising literacy skills to deal with body image portrayals in television advertisements. In particular, the study addresses Spanish schoolchildren (6 to 9 years old) from Barcelona.

1.1 Advertising Literacy: Dimensions of Analysis

Almost everybody is seduced by the tyranny of the body in advertising. However, while some people focus on songs, colors, and logos, others appreciate the characterization of the characters, praising their charm, personality, and body appearance. Children's curiosity and engagement with the advertising make them an easy target for false body images (Harrison & Hefner, 2014). The presentation of unrealistic images by advertising producers leaves children susceptible to poor self-perception, misconceptions, and the spread of unhealthy myths and stereotypes (Fanjul-Peyró *et al.*, 2019; Jiménez-Morales *et al.*, 2020; Lapierre, 2017). To counteract these negative effects, media education has proven to be an effective method to protect the child audience. Recent approaches such as Advertising Literacy offer various opportunities to understand how children perceive and analyze body image in advertising.

Academic literature has employed different terms to describe Advertising Literacy. The most commonly used definition conceptualizes it as children's ability to recognize, evaluate, and understand advertising (Spielvogel & Terlutter, 2013). More recent approaches such as the model suggested by Hudders *et al.* (2017) to process embedded advertising formats, prefer to describe Advertising Literacy as a multi-faceted construct with distinct dimensions and levels of analysis (Figure 1).

From a general viewpoint, Advertising Literacy should be considered as the innate response of children to mitigate the impact of advertising. For this response to be effectively activated, children must develop two critical dimensions: the ability to manage their emotional responses and to assess advertising. As noted by Hudders *et al.* (2016), children develop their advertising skills as they acquire both *declarative/factual knowledge*, or domain-specific content (which is related to the market principles). Furthermore, children must possess *procedural knowledge*, which enables them to make inferences about the factual knowledge of advertising and evaluate it.

Figure 1

The Role of Advertising Literacy in Children's Processing of Advertising. Hudders et al. (2017)

Hudders *et al.* (2017) categorize both types of knowledge as *dispositional* (factual knowledge) and *situational* (procedural knowledge) advertising literacies. Dispositional advertising literacy encompasses the knowledge, skills, and abilities that children possess regarding the persuasive nature of advertising. It can be seen as the network of informational nodes that become activated when children confront advertising. The development of dispositional advertising literacy encompasses cognitive, affective, and moral meanings related to advertising. As children gain knowledge about advertising, they are able to control their emotional responses and develop judgment. On the other hand, situational advertising literacy refers to the practical use and application of dispositional knowledge. This involves the thoughts and actions that children take in direct response to the persuasive intent of advertising, such as recognizing advertisements and critically reflecting on their message. Critical reflection entails the recognition of advertising tactics and evaluating their accuracy. The development of situational advertising literacy requires children to have control over their impulses, attention, and emotions.

Hudders *et al.* (2017) also identify a third dimension of analysis, coping skills, which are defined as children's ability to recognize, analyze, interpret, evaluate, and remember the persuasive attempts of advertising and to execute strategies to effectively deal with these messages. Coping skills are an essential link between dispositional and situational advertising literacy. They determine the speed and accuracy with which the informational nodes

(cognitive, moral, and affective) can be activated in dispositional advertising literacy, and they help children to choose the appropriate strategy to respond to the advertising message.

From our analysis, the multi-faceted model proposed by Hudders *et al.* (2017) is a valuable systematization of a vast corpus of research that approaches the study of advertising literacy. One of its strengths is its focus on analyzing both the cognitive and sociocultural dimensions of advertising. The model takes into account both the direct and indirect responses children have to advertising, considering not only their informational interactions but also the socialization that occurs when they are exposed to it. This is especially useful for addressing gaps in media and body image research, as it can inform questions such as "how do children interact with the body image they see in advertisements?" (Sánchez-Reina, 2020a).

Moreover, the integration of the Hudders *et al.* model can also be useful as a component of advertising literacy training programs designed to address the impact of body image portrayed in advertisements. Evaluating children's competencies in interacting with depicted body images can provide valuable insights into their strengths and weaknesses to deal with images. The objective of this study was therefore to examine young children's advertising literacy skills in relation to their ability to process body image in television advertisements. The study specifically addressed three research questions: (RQ1) How do young children understand depictions of body image in television advertisements? (RQ2) How do children respond to misleading messages about body image in advertisements? (RQ3) What coping mechanisms do young children exhibit when viewing depicted body image in advertising? As follows, we introduce the design and results of the study.

2. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHOD

We designed an exploratory qualitative study with primary schoolchildren. The sample consisted of 58 students (24 boys and 34 girls), from the first, second, and third grades. The mean age of the participants was 8,0 years old. All of the students were enrolled in either public or charter schools in Barcelona.

Convenience sampling was used to recruit the participants. Researchers contacted five schools that had previously participated in the study (Sánchez-Reina *et al.* 2023). After revising the agreements of collaboration, the school board invited families to join the study. In accordance with the ethical protocols of the leading university, a consent form was sent to the children's families to inform them about the research and its purpose.

The methodological strategy included the implementation of gamified focus groups (N= 10) (Colucci, 2007). The focus groups took place as part of a Media Literacy workshop and were conducted in the schools as extracurricular activities. Interviewers introduced themselves as instructors to give a talk about Media and Advertising.

As part of the workshop dynamic, children were invited to play a board game where the focus group was set. This gamification of the focus groups created a friendly environment that allowed the children to produce more genuine and naturalistic responses compared to a structured interview setting. The game was named “*Guess who I am*” and as part of the game directions, students were asked to choose a character from visual cards and make a story to describe themselves.

The visual cards corresponded to screenshots from popular advertising, addressed to young children as identified in a former study (Sánchez-Reina, 2020b). Children chose as many cards as turns and participants earned points if they gave correct answers. Following a conversational strategy, instructors/researchers introduced prompts and questions to produce discussion within the group. For instance, “Would this character be a woman in a sports advertisement?”. Focus groups were videotaped and voice recorded. Additionally, a supporting researcher took notes of the relevant events during the session.

The qualitative approach adopted in this study focused on analyzing children’s advertising literacy, specifically by observing their decodification of advertising messages and understanding of body image portrayals. This included observing both dispositional and situational skills, as well as their understanding of body image.

As part of the protocol of analysis, we fully transcribed the focus groups. Participants’ names and any other personal information were pseudonymized; e.g., an alias replaced the names in the transcriptions to protect the children’s identity. Once the material was fully transcribed, we exported it along with advertisements visuals, and fieldwork notes to the software Atlas.ti 9.

We conducted a thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2014). The first level of analysis consisted of identifying excerpts related to children’s understandings of advertising; for example, their automatic responses expressing their feelings and attitudes. This analysis resulted in 510 codes grouped into 10 broad topics. The second level of analysis explored the codes and categories derived from the analysis of dispositional and situational advertising literacies. This resulted in 424 codes, which were grouped based on similarities and eventually formed six thematic clusters. The next section reports the results concerning the research questions formulated in the context of this paper.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Children's understanding of depicted body image

As part of the first research question (RQ1), “How do children understand depicted body image in advertising?”, the analysis showed three relevant outputs:

- a) Children engage with advertisements by admiring the body image of the characters, specifically praising aspects such as beauty and the attractiveness of facial features (e.g. hair, teeth, eyes).
- b) Children have emotional reactions to characters based on their appearance. Characters are associated with moral values and their descriptions can reveal attitudes and feelings.
- c) Children categorize characters' appearance based on societal norms and values. Beauty is perceived as good while ugliness is often linked to negative traits.

As observed in the focus groups, children tend to remember and connect with characters based on their physical appearance. Many children describe characters based on their attractive features such as hair, face, and body type. The appearance of characters is often linked to their social traits and reinforces the idea that good looks equate to good character roles within advertising storylines. For example, *“He’s the handsome boy, so he’s the good student. He also has that gentle look,”* said Miriam in Focus Group 6. *“She’s so beautiful, she is a good friend,”* said María in Focus Group 3. Attractiveness in characters is often contrasted with ugliness and the negative traits associated with the character's role and performance. *“The guy from the cereal commercial is the bad guy. He isn’t friendly. He’s ugly,”* said Xavi in Focus Group 5. *“The woman from the Lidl ad is...ugly. She looks like a terrorist. Look at her face, her hands,”* said Adriá in Focus Group 8.

Children's responses to advertising portrayals are often accompanied by emotional reactions. On the one hand, they connect the character's personality with feelings and emotions [mostly stereotyped]. They observe happy and excited characters as reliable. *“I really like them because they’re happy,”* said Laia in Focus Group 2. In contrast, they perceive those characters looking sad, annoyed, or confused as unconfident. *“She’s strange. She’s confused. I don’t trust her,”* said Manel in Focus Group 9. On the other hand, when children tell stories focusing on the characters, they may reenact with the same attitude as observed in the announcements. They may not recall the brands or products, but they may be willing to dramatize to express what they saw in the ad and how they felt about it. This is also evident

through their singing songs, mimicking of actors, and recreating situations as observed in the following excerpt:

“One thing, I’ve watched a perfume advertisement. There was a lady in the car, she was driving too fast [*The participant dramatizes the situation in front of the group, waving her hand and fingers*]. She gets out of the car so quickly and says: ‘Chloé’ [*The participant leans her body and mimics the pronunciation. She laughs*] [*Group laughs*].” [Berta, Focus Group 9].

Children’s perceptions of attractiveness in characters were largely objectified and driven by their curiosity or interest. As observed in the focus groups, many children consistently focused on a beautiful or attractive face as a reason to be friends with or talk to the character. They link the characters’ physical appearance with their perceived traits such as personality, attitudes, and roles. Although these descriptions are largely based on inferences (beliefs, and stereotypes) advertising message operates as a legitimizing context for interpretations. “*The young girl, with a ponytail, looks friendly. Well, I know she’s friendly. We could play together,*” said Jenny in Focus Group 5. “*He’s handsome and pleasant. As far as I know, he helps his mother with the house chores,*” said Diego in Focus Group 10. Overall, the perception of characters was largely influenced by their physical appearance and the sociocultural norms in which the children lived. “*She’s a bad girl. She has an ugly face and she’s rejecting you with her movements. She’s telling you, you’ve done it badly,*” said Albert in Focus Group 2.

As observed in the focus groups, most children base their descriptions of characters on their knowledge of advertisements, as well as their own perceptions and judgments. However, the use of stereotypes is also common in their narratives. Both boys and girls tend to praise stereotypical images to describe the body image of characters, particularly when discussing the concept of beauty. Children consistently describe blond and white characters as beautiful, and this notion applies not only to female characters but also to white male characters. Children rely on the Western standard of beauty to distinguish positive and negative body image, which is linked to values, attitudes, and behaviors, as shown in the following passages:

Researcher: Laia, you chose a character who has medium-length hair, why?

Laia: I don’t know. I think he looks handsome. Because he’s blond and he’s handsome.

Researcher: What if the character were dark skin and dark-haired?

Laia: He wouldn’t be so handsome anymore, like this other one.

Researcher: What if we dyed his hair blond?

Ara: No, no. He would be looking so bad because he is a brunette guy.

[*Laia & Ara, Focus Group 2*]

Researcher: Why do you think she is beautiful?

Alberto: Because she looks like a Barbie. She is a Barbie, and she has blond hair and she has lipstick. I think she's beautiful.

[*Alberto, Focus Group 2*]

3.2. Responding to misleading body image messages

Regarding the second research question (RQ2), "How do children respond to misleading messages about body image in advertisements?", the qualitative analysis led to three significant conclusions:

- a) Children exhibit ambiguous responses to depicted body images. On the one hand, they react positively to portrayals, aligned with their societal body values, but on the other hand, they are skeptical of these images due to their inoculated advertising literacy skills.
- b) Children are capable of critically analyzing advertising content. Although their different levels of development conditioned their ability to master specific literacy skills, most children can recognize and analyze advertising production tactics and techniques.
- c) Children's critical skills towards advertising make them reflect on the instrumentalization and commodification of the body, including aspects such as the use of beauty ideals and the sexualization of characters.

As observed in the previous section, focus groups revealed that children evaluate physical appearance according to conventional standards of beauty. They confidently describe characters using stereotypes to discuss their body image, praising beauty, whiteness, and slimness. However, many of them also express skepticism about the naturalness of images, warning about the use of editing in advertising, as exemplified in the following excerpt:

Iris: I really like Shakira. She's so beautiful.

Carla: [*Looking closely at the image*] They have changed her face. She's changed something.

Óscar: She's ugly in the real life [*laughs*]

Celia: Well, she's on television, they make her look beautiful.

Iris: It happens in all movies.

[*Carla, Óscar, Celia & Iris, Focus Group 8*].

Most children are capable of discussing the production techniques used in advertising and how they influence consumers. Younger children tend to reflect on camera angles and shots as a means of distorting images, while older children show more critical analysis and discuss advertisers' tactics for enhancing body image and appearance. Children are able to recognize the use of image editing, such as photoshop to make characters appear slimmer, whiter, and wrinkle-free. This practice is not limited to advertising, as children also associate image alteration with the media representation of celebrities. The widespread use of airbrushing in media and television production prompts children to exercise caution and employ their media literacy skills to differentiate between altered and authentic images, particularly when evaluating images of celebrities.

José: This woman is photoshopped.

Researcher: What do you see photoshopped in the image?

José: Her eyes.

Tania: Her face.

Marta: Her lips.

Manel: This is whiter [refers to her hair].

[*José, Tania, Marta & Manel, Focus Group 9*]

Gaby: This was edited on the computer.

Alex: Her lips are very red.

Gaby: Like Shakira, everything is ... Everything... Well, her teeth were edited on the computer.

[*Gaby & Alex, Focus Group 7*]

The enhancement of body image in advertisements is not only tied to promoting beauty but also to the commodification of the body. The older children, for instance, were consistent in their assessment, stating that image editing is employed to capture the viewer's attention. They view the depiction of attractive bodies in advertisements as a way to elicit a positive reaction from the audience and inspire them. As Gaby from focus group 7 stated, "*Advertisers choose handsome actors to impress people,*" and Manel from focus group 9 added, "*There's a hunky guy who recommends it, then you will buy it.*" The beauty of models is seen as a key component of the persuasive tactics used in advertising messages, as evidenced in the following excerpt.

Researcher: You said that she is a beautiful person and that's the reason why she can be on television. Why is that?

Sara: Yeah! Well, because if she were ugly, nobody would hire her to do TV commercials...[...] Nobody would buy what she is selling.

[Sara, Focus Group 1]

The commodification of the body is not only discussed because of the advertisers' selection of attractive models but also in the way advertisers show specific body parts (e.g., legs, abdomen, torso). Children recall various advertisements that employ partial nudity, particularly in advertisements for perfumes and hygiene products, which not included in the focus group, were mentioned during the focus groups. (Figure 2).

Figure 2

The commodification of the body in advertising as declared by participating children

Note: Children's examples of nudity in advertising brought in focus groups included beauty and hygiene products such as soaps, shampoo, and perfumes. 1) Paco Rabanne and 2) Gabrielle Chanel.

Children exhibit a strong critical stance toward the depiction of nudity in advertising. There is a consistent agreement among them that many of these depictions are unnecessary and therefore its use illicit as advertisers used nudity to sell any products. Moreover, the moral judgment of some children is also present in their evaluations as some of them perceived these images as sexualized (for the interest of adults) and inappropriate for children, as expressed by Carla from Focus Group 8:

Researcher: Why do you say it is bad?

Carla: Because... let's see [she laughs]. You can look at her intimate parts [laughs] and the boys can make a picture of her and... [laughs] ... Look, it's a moisturizer, a cream for the legs! Advertisers have to show her whole body [laughs]. What I do not understand is why...

Iris: Look, the naked girl that shows Lizipaina. She is naked for you, to buy the product. [...] She has to be dressed.

Carla: It's not about the cream. It's the naked woman.

[Carla & Iris, Focus Group 8]

Nevertheless, the depiction of nudity in advertising is also trivialized and children legitimize the commodification of the body. While some children concentrate on the moral judgment of nudity, others seek to understand the reason to show some nudity. For example,

Siara and Leo from Focus Group 6 agreed that in some ads, partial nudity is necessary to show how the product works “*how efficient it is*” or “*how healthy your skin can be*”.

3.3. Coping mechanisms to deal with depicted body image

With regards to the analysis of coping mechanisms displayed by young children when viewing body image in advertising (third research question), the analysis resulted in two important conclusions that help in understanding the role of advertising literacy:

- a) Children are drawn to attractive characters, but many of them are able to question the accuracy of their beauty and appearance based on their understanding of image and video production.
- b) Children are influenced by stereotypical images of beauty and attractiveness such as the white, blonde, and slim/muscle-fit ideal, but they are able to make sense of narratives and images through the counter-narratives provided by media, advertising, and adult mediation.

As observed in the focus groups, children tend to question beauty and attractiveness as an immediate response to advertising messages. Their curiosity about character appearance and performance is accompanied by the knowledge that debunks the reality of character portrayals. Statements such as “*They made her look beautiful*” and “*He has a special costume to have big muscles*” show their awareness of body image. In sum, children's preference for character appearance is not at odds with their ability to judge the production of body image, which is beneficial as it makes them feel informed and protected from misleading advertising intentions.

Similarly, children who love imagining compelling stories also enjoy exposing the reality behind what they see. They evaluate audiovisual production as a tool to make advertising ads attractive. Many of them approve of the use of advertising effects while many others disapprove of its negative practices. Children's moral judgment serves as a main coping skill in questioning the purpose of images and being mindful of advertisements. It is worth noting that many children may support their reflection on information coming from advertising literacy mediation, school teachers, parents, and even advertising campaigns.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The present study aimed to analyze young children's advertising literacy skills to deal with body image portrayed in television advertisements. The results of the study reveal remarkable conclusions, as different levels of advertising literacy have been identified. In accordance with recent studies on advertising literacy (Feijoo & Sádaba, 2022; Hwang *et al.*, 2018; Hudders *et al.*, 2017), our study highlights both dispositional and situational advertising literacies that mediate in children's understanding of body image in advertising, likewise, it illustrates the coping mechanisms that children exhibit to deal with advertising

Regarding our first research question, "How do children understand depicted body image in advertising?" The results show that children praise characters based on their physical appearance, exhibiting emotional reactions and positive attitudes. They perceive character portrayals as conforming to body stereotypes. These findings are in line with prior research (Götz & Herche, 2012), which suggests that children associate attractiveness with stereotypes of whiteness, slenderness, and gender roles. The results highlight the strong connection that children have with media stereotypes and the role that advertising plays in perpetuating body ideals (Zayer *et al.*, 2019). Children are drawn to stereotyped beauty as advertising legitimizes the characters portrayed and society endorses these portrayals as the norm, the normal, and the ethos to be normalized.

Concerning the second research question, how children respond to misleading messages about body image in advertising, our analysis revealed that most children are aware of the production techniques used in advertising and are capable of critically analyzing these messages. As demonstrated by Buckingham (2013), children exhibit agency as active readers of advertising and possess an understanding of what occurs beyond the visual representations on the screen. They have the ability to discuss advertising features such as airbrushing, camera effects, shots, and angles, as well as the motivations behind the use of these techniques by advertisers. However, it should be noted that there may be disparities in the literacy levels among children. While younger children are able to identify basic advertising techniques, older children possess a more nuanced understanding of post-production techniques.

The critical outlook of many children enables them to critique the persuasive intent of advertisements, particularly in sensitive issues, such as the commodification of the body. As observed in the focus groups, children are particularly critical of advertisements that feature partial nudity, perceiving the instrumentalization of the body as an unfair tactic to persuade adult consumers. Conversely, children also show curiosity to describe the messages that commodify the body. Despite feelings of both fun and embarrassment, children are willing to discuss messages that "they see but don't like," connecting partial nudity with sexual imagery (Merskin, 2004).

In regards to the third research question, our study has found that despite the fact that young children enjoy fantasy and mysticism in advertising, they are capable of recognizing its deceptive nature. Children are able to question the authenticity and suitability of images presented and understand the advertising narratives through and can make sense of advertising narratives mediated by both its content and the adult mediation. Similar to the findings of Diedrichs *et al.* (2011), young children demonstrate critical perspectives towards advertising tactics and objectives. However, compared to teenagers and adults, their coping abilities may be influenced by their level of development and exposure to media literacy.

Aligned with similar studies (Hudders *et al.*, 2017, 2018; Rozendaal *et al.*, 2011a), our study shows that young children aged 6 to 9 years old are influenced by body image in advertising as well as they possess abilities to understand and counteract its messages. However, to increase and keep their situational awareness, intervention in advertising literacy is necessary. Children's relationship with the media environment provides them with a critical understanding to understand images and videos (Sánchez-Reina *et al.*, 2021; Rodríguez-Rementería, 2022). The new media formats and the use of digital devices can be beneficial to enhance their advertising skills. Moreover, families and educators should also focus on reinforcing both the affective and moral domains, which may also contribute to developing advertising literacies.

This qualitative study has some important limitations. Firstly, the sample of participant children does not represent the diversity of the Spanish child population. In terms of diversity, the study addresses data from middle-class students, living in the urban area of Barcelona and with diverse media consumption. Additionally, many of the participants demonstrated prior knowledge of advertising literacy due to the school intervention. The results should be carefully interpreted assuming that the interviewed children had been exposed (at any time) exposed to any literacy training. It is important that future research include a wider and more diverse school population, besides children with no prior media education training. Furthermore, future research should also consider using new research methods to provide stronger evidence on Spanish children's understanding of advertising.

Advertising literacy is a promising approach for exploring children's understanding of advertising. In the context of this research, advertising literacy has contributed to a better understanding of how Spanish children understand body image portrayals in advertising and provides new insights to integrate into children's advertising education. Therefore, we recommend considering our conclusions as an opportunity to design and implement both advertising literacy interventions and further research.

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